

EFFECTIVENESS OF CONTEXTUALIZED LEARNING MATERIAL IN TEACHING MOTHER TONGUE 3

¹ARLITA D. LARDIZABAL, ²JOHNNY S. BANTULO, EdD,
³EMELYN E. ORIAS, MIE

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges, Graduate School
General Santos City, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7977151>

Published Date: 18-April-2023

Abstract: This study examined the effectiveness of contextualized learning material in teaching Mother Tongue 3. The subjects were the 33 Grade three learners of Wali Integrated School for the school year 2021-2022. The study used the single group experimental research design, particularly the one group pre-test, post-test experimental design because only one group was used in the study. The pre-test and post-test were administered to the respondents at the first and end of the first quarter before and after they had completed the contextualized learning content respectively. The researcher used a t-test in treating the data. The findings of the study reveal that contextualized learning material in teaching Mother Tongue was effective.

Keywords: Contextualized learning materials, grade 3 learners, mother tongue, educational management, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Teachers can effectively educate the learners when they employ resources based on two factors: the defined government curriculum goals and the learners' existing understanding, culture, and value systems. Only a few books are available for most of the 170 languages of the Philippines, and materials development appears a daunting task. Nonetheless, books remain one of the most essential materials for learners' learning. Teaching and learning cannot be effective without adequate and relevant use of instructional materials. These learning materials are highly regarded as tools for the improvement of learners' achievement, and the use of appropriate learning material has a strong relationship and plays a vital role in improving the academic performance of the learners (Ahmadi and Reza, 2018; Kirkpatrick, 2017; Stronge, 2018).

In fact, the only reading materials available to children in most underdeveloped nations are textbooks, which are typically in low supply. Learners struggle to learn and become literate when they do not have access to appropriate materials in most low- and middle-income countries. Most primary schools lack a library. Books are considered a luxury that most families cannot afford and textbooks in the local language are uncommon. In the Philippine educational setting in implementing mother tongue-based instruction, the teachers face challenges, such as the unavailability of books written in the mother tongue, lack of vocabulary, and shortage of teachers' training. The learners' materials and other textbooks are inadequate as well, as instructional materials. This situation has a significant impact on the teaching-learning process and the program's smooth implementation in general, particularly on learners' academic performance in Mother Tongue, where teaching Mother Tongue to Wali Integrated School learners has also been a challenge in this context (Amin and Sundari, 2020; Mangila, 2019; Mupa and Isaac Chinooneka, 2019).

Moreover, the use of contextualized materials helps the learners acquire new skills and knowledge, improves their learning experiences, increases learners' motivation, persistence, and outcomes, and develops their abilities and attitudes. They are

motivated to learn and to take part in the learning process. Contextual teaching and learning help the teachers and the learners relate the meaning through prior and new knowledge to get a new understanding making the learning more meaningful because the learners enjoy their learning. It improves learners' recall and comprehension of the idea. The learners can retain, recollect, and comprehend the content because they are learning through the material derived from their own experiences and new knowledge (Chen, Wang, Zou, Lin, Xie and Tsai, 2020; Philippines Department of Education Order No. 16, s.2012; Us Saqlain, Shafqat and Hassan, 2020).

With this, knowing the importance of contextualized curriculum and its impact on learners' learning outcomes, the researcher was inspired to contextualize learning materials that were used as supplementary materials to encourage learners to acquire and participate in the learning process in order to improve their academic performance in their mother-tongue.

Therefore, the purpose of this research was to determine the effectiveness of contextualized learning material in teaching Mother Tongue 3 in improving the learning performance of Wali Integrated School Grade 3 learners.

1.1 Statement of The Problem:

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of using contextualized learning material in teaching Mother Tongue among the Grade 3 learners of Wali Integrated School, Wali, Maitum, Sarangani Province, during 2021-2022.

Precisely, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the pre-test scores of the grade 3 learners in Mother Tongue?
2. What are their post-test scores?
3. Is there a significant difference between the mean gain scores of the pre-test and post-test of the subjects in Mother Tongue after the treatment?

Hypothesis. H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean gain scores of Grade 3 learners after the treatment.

1.2 Theoretical Framework

This study was based on the concept of constructivism by Jean Piaget (1936) that humans generate knowledge through the interaction between their experiences and ideas. The measure of motivation for learning relies on the learner, not the instructor or teacher. It asserts that the learners are continuously updating their memory based on continuing experience. Constructivists claim that because learners can generate meaning in relationship to experience, every learner's version of the world is unique, even familiar concepts (Deslauriers, McCarty, Miller, Callaghan, and Kestin, 2019; Kintu, Zhu, and Kagambe, 2017; Shawky and Badawi, 2019).

On the other hand, Lev Vygotsky's theory of cognitive development, claims that social connections influence how children's intelligence and thought processes develop. Based on this theory, he proposes that culture plays a significant role in developing specific abilities such as learning, memory, attention, and problem-solving. Culturally specific tools, most significantly, the learning styles, influence how children reflect on the world around them. His perception of the zone of proximal development — also known as the zone of potential development, is based on the idea that learners learn best when they can complete an assignment independently but are not quite there. That is where a teacher, parent, or other adult comes in, gradually removing assistance until the child can complete the task independently. Learners could achieve a much greater level of learning through the help of a More Knowledgeable Other (instructor). Thus, in the classroom context, learning takes place when teachers can present information in a way that pupils can construct, which means based on their own experiences, and that is anchoring teaching in the diverse life context of the learners (Dastpak, Behjat, and Taghinezhad, 2017; Moust, Bouhuijs, and Schmidt, 2021; Taber, 2020).

Moreover, Ausubel's Theory of Assimilation focuses on "meaningful learning," as he defines it. It is a procedure in which new information is linked to an existing relevant aspect of a person's knowledge structure. This theory combines cognitive, affective, and psychomotor functions. It also distinguishes between two types of learning: rote learning and meaningful learning. For a young learner, rote learning entails recall and transferability. The learners are given the freedom to learn when and how they want in this theory (Agra, Formiga, Oliveira, Costa, Fernandes, and Nóbrega, 2019; Brown, 2017; Çeliköz, Erişen, and Şahin, 2019).

Finally, John Dewey's learning-by-doing theory proposed that the utmost way for humans to learn is through a "hands-on" method. This theory means that to adapt and learn, students must interact with their surroundings. The same was true for

teachers, who had to learn alongside their learners, which was crucial in establishing progressive education practices. People build their representations and incorporate new information into their pre-existing knowledge as they experience the world and reflect on it (Barzilai, Zohar and Mor-Hagani, 2018; Clark, 2018; Huijgen, van de Grift, van Boxtel and Holthuis, 2018).

1.3 Conceptual Framework

The study's conceptual framework can be depicted in Figure 1. The figure showed the process of conducting the research. The pre-test can be depicted in the following figures placed in the first box. The pre-test was given to the 33 subjects before the start of the course to determine their initial understanding of the learning objectives' measurements.

After the pre-test, the treatment then was conducted which can be seen in the second box; students were exposed in learning the mother tongue using the contextualized learning materials created by the researcher which served as the intervention. It was based on Mother Tongue Grade 3's Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) for the first quarter, weeks 1 to 8.

Moreover, after the treatment, the post-test was given to the 33 subjects after an eight-week intervention to determine what they had learned after using the learning material. Post-test can be seen in the third box.

The pre-test and post-test assessed how much knowledge a learner had gained in a particular subject. So, the test included questions on all topics covered during the semester. The researcher allotted a numerical score to both the pre-test and the post-test when rating the tests. The difference between the mean gain scores of the two variables determines the effectiveness of the contextualized material.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study used the single group experimental research design with the use of pre-test and post-test because only one group was used. It utilized a pre-test or baseline observation (O_1) which allowed the researcher to determine the effects of the treatment by comparing pre-test and post-test (O_2) results. This kind of design used the pre-test and post-test to gather the data which the respondents studied before and after the experimental manipulation (Pandey and Pandey, 2021).

Meanwhile, the contextualized learning material was used for eight (8) weeks, quarter 1. The research and development method produces a particular product and test its effectiveness. Research development is defined as a purpose to result in the products and ends with an evaluation process (Chapelle, Kremmel, and Brindley, 2019).

Because only one group would be used in the study, this study employed a pre-test, post-test experimental design. It has been used in educational research that involves experimental groups, as clearly presented in Figure 1 (Strickland-Davis, Kosloski, and Reed, 2020).

Experimental Group O_1 X O_2

where:

- O_1 refers to the pre-test result in Mother Tongue of the experimental group
- O_2 refers to the post-test result in Mother Tongue of the experimental group
- X refers to the use of contextualized learning materials

2.2 Research Locale

This research was conducted in Wali Integrated School (formerly Wali Elementary School), East Maitum District. It is located at Barangay Wali, Maitum, Sarangani Province. It was established in 1963. It comprises 28 teachers, wherein 12 are elementary teachers, 13 are junior high school teachers, and 3 are senior high school teachers. Since its creation as an integrated school in 2011, the school is continuously increasing its enrolment, which is now 320 from elementary, 220 from Junior High School, and 65 from Senior High School.

2.3 Research Respondents

The mentioned school comprises a diverse group of students; most of them are T'boli, Ilocano, B'laan, Maruri, Tagakaulo, and Muslim are among the others. Morning Star, Greenfield, and Rising Sun are the three puroks of the barangay where the respondents live.

The study's subjects were the thirty-three (33) Wali Integrated School Grade 3 learners in the school year 2021-2022. Because this study used a single group design, they were all considered. The table below shows the subjects of the study.

According to the table, eleven (11) learners live in Purok Morning Star, seven (7) in Purok Greenfield, thirteen (13) learners live in Purok Morning Star, one (1) learner lives in Barangay Pangi, and one (1) learner lives in Barangay Malalag.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents

Respondents	Total
Purok Morning Star	11
Purok Greenfield	7
Purok Rising Sun	13
Barangay Pangi	1
Barangay Malalag	1
Total	33

2.4 Research Instrument

This study relied on a questionnaire created by the researcher. It was supported by a Table of Specifications that used Bloom's Taxonomy of percentages to design the questions, with 60% easy, 30% average, and 10% of tough questions, respectively. The questions were based on Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) for Mother Tongue grade three first quarter. The experts evaluated the mentioned instrument before the researcher utilized it.

Initially, the proponent created a 60-item test instrument based on first grading lessons and a Table of Specifications (TOS). The researcher's completed questionnaire had undergone validation with the expert, five master teachers. After the expert finished checking and validating each question, they suggested that the researcher needed to follow the blooms taxonomy of percentages in making the questionnaire and arranged it into three levels which were 60% for Easy questions, 30% for Average queries, and 10% for difficult questions. The expert validated the final number of questions used by the researcher in her study, sixty (60) questions with the specifications table. After the expert validated the questionnaire, the researcher submitted it to her adviser for correction and suggestion and ensured the reliability of the instruments.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher created an official 30-item test from the additional materials she utilized in the pre-test and post-test based on the 60-item test in Mother Tongue 3 that went through validation and piloting.

The researcher had the instrument validated by five expert validators. When designing the questionnaire, their suggestions and criticisms were taken into consideration. Validity tests, including test analysis, were also carried out.

After the researcher completed the procedures for piloting and validating the research instrument until it was determined to be valid and reliable, she asked the school head and barangay for permission to administer the questionnaire. The pre-test was done one-on-one with each subject, going from house to house to ensure that everyone took the test while adhering to the health guidelines. Each subject was given an individual test paper and was instructed and supervised by the researcher while taking the test. She collected the test papers, checked, and encoded the scores for processing and interpretation after they finished the test.

In this procedure, the subjects were relatively compelled to answer the questions. Furthermore, the return rate was high, and the researcher could answer any unclear questions (Gehlbach and Artino, 2018).

The Contextualized Learning Material was based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) of Mother Tongue 3 for the first quarter consisting of eight weeks. It was designed in a modular format which was modified and contextualized from the self-learning module and learning materials from the Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS).

Relatively, the DepEd was digitizing all existing DepEd-developed K–12 teaching and learning materials, as well as emerging new digital, interactive, and print-based materials associated with the new curriculum. It was disseminated via LRMDS to all DepEd regions, divisions, schools, and learning centers. Additionally, each activity in the CLM was contextualized, which meant that the examples, tasks, and items in the material were relevant to the learners. The activities were created applying the four A's of learning: the activity, analysis, abstraction, and assessment. The first activity in the module was designed to stimulate the learners' previous knowledge of the lesson. This activity helped the learners understand what they already knew and clarified with what they had learned next. The activity for analysis was the second part. It was created to gain new knowledge. Another phase in which the learners processed and classified what was valid and what was not was a more in-depth understanding of the lesson.

Moreover, the learners gained a broader perspective of the lesson while getting closer to the main topic. The application of knowledge was the third part. This section's activity entirely focused on the presented lesson, with more lead questions to guide learners in reinforcing what they already knew and should know more. The learners here began to understand the significance of the lesson and its relevance to their lives. Finally, the last A was the assessment of knowledge or the evaluation of knowledge. The goal of this stage was to get the learners to think about new methods to improve what they had learned and to put them into practice (Anderson, 2018; Burden, 2020; Henriksen, Richardson, and Mehta, 2017).

Like the research instrument, the contextualized learning material was validated by five experts. There were six indicators to consider in validating the material. These are 1.) objectives; 2.) technical quality; 3.) instructional quality; 4.) organization; 5.) language arts content, and 6.) alignment, which was adapted from a published study. The material received an overall mean of 4.70. It meant excellent. Based on this result, the contextualized learning material was suitable and appropriate for learners to master the competency.

The occurrence of the Covid-19 pandemic has affected the country, particularly the education sector. Still, the Department of Education has pursued to continue delivering quality education to its clientele without exposing the health and safety of the learners, teachers, and its personnel. Thus, following the suspension of the face-to-face schooling, the school adopted modular distance learning, which has been the most appropriate learning modality in a community where there is no internet connection to conduct online learning (Philippines Department of Education Order No. 012, s.2020).

The Modular Distance Learning (MDL) is a type of individualized instruction that allows learners to utilize self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy. The teachers support parents in facilitating their children at home, particularly those in kindergarten through grade three. Any family member or other stakeholder in the community serves as a para-teacher (Cooper, Lindsay, and Nye, 2000; Natividad, 2021).

Following the school's distribution and retrieval scheme and schedule, the material was distributed every Monday of the week in the preceding scenario, and it was retrieved the following Monday.

In place of this scenario, parents/guardians were informed about the study, the procedures, and their role in administering the material to ensure that the subjects' answers were accurate and valid. In this regard, the role of parents was critical in their learners' learning because, in the absence of teachers, parental support was vital to learners' learning development (Đurišić and Bunijevac, 2017; Lara and Saracosti, 2019; Lau and Lee, 2021).

During this phase, the researcher did home visits to learners for assistance, follow-up, and monitoring of their progress regularly without compromising their safety and health. Health protocols were observed. The parents or guardians and the learners were instructed to reach the researcher via text message, note, letter, and chat messaging. These interventions were made to ensure that every problem would be addressed accordingly and promptly.

Finally, at the end of the first quarter, the researcher gave each subject a one-on-one post-test. After the subjects had completed the test, the test papers were collected. For processing and interpretation, the test papers were checked and logged. The scores were logged and compared to the pre-test results to determine the effectiveness of the learning material.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Pre-test Scores of Grade 3 Learners in Mother Tongue

Table 2: The table presents the pre-test scores of Grade three learners in Mother Tongue before the treatment.

Pupil	Score	Percentage	Description
1	10	33%	Low
2	13	43%	Average
3	16	53%	Average
4	5	17%	Very Low
5	9	30%	Low
6	6	20%	Very Low
7	11	37%	Low
8	7	23%	Low
9	4	13%	Very Low
10	18	60%	Average
11	18	60%	Average
12	10	33%	Low
13	12	40%	Low
14	15	50%	Average
15	12	40%	Low
16	12	40%	Low
17	9	30%	Low
18	6	20%	Very Low
19	11	37%	Low
20	5	17%	Very Low
21	6	20%	Very Low
22	5	17%	Very Low
23	18	60%	Average
24	19	63%	High
25	18	60%	Average
26	19	63%	High
27	12	40%	Low
28	12	40%	Low
29	12	40%	Low
30	13	43%	Average
31	14	47%	Average
32	15	50%	Average
33	12	40%	Low
Total	384	1280	
Mean Score	11.64	38.79	Low

It can be noticed that none of the 33 learners received a very high score. However, two learners, or 6% of the total population, received a score of 19, which was considered a high score. They were learners 24 and 26. Learners 2, 3, 10, 11, 14, 23, 26, 30, 31 and 32 received scores of 13, 16, 18, 18, 15, 18, 18, 13, 14 and 15 respectively, implying that 10 out of 33 or 30% of the learners received average scores.

On the other hand, it was observed that the majority of the subjects received low pre-test scores. Learners 1, 5, 7, 8, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 19, 27, 28, 29 and 33 received 10, 9, 11, 7, 10, 12, 12, 12, 9, 11, 12, 12, 12 and 12. This means that 14 learners, or 42 percent, get low marks. In the pre-test result, 7 or 21% of the learners received very low scores. They were learners

4, 6, 9, 18, 20, 21, and 22 with scores of 5, 6, 4, 6, 5, 6, and 5. Generally, the mean of the 33 learners for the pre-test was 11.64, which is considered a low performance.

The finding was supported by Gess-Newsome, Taylor, Carlson, Gardner, Wilson, and Stuhlsatz (2019), who found that learners who lack learning materials struggled with the subject and who had little prior knowledge were more likely to reflect on highlighted errors. Also, this supports the studies that learners who were taught with instructional materials outperformed those who were not. The use of instructional materials generally enhanced learners’ understanding of concepts and led to academic accomplishment (Koh, Lee, and Lim, 2018; Smallhorn, 2017).

3.2 Post-test Scores of Grade 3 Learners in Mother Tongue

Table 3: The table shows the post-test scores of Grade 3 learners in Mother Tongue after the treatment.

Pupil	Score	Percentage	Description
1	11	37%	Low
2	19	63%	High
3	23	77%	High
4	11	37%	Low
5	17	57%	Average
6	10	33%	Low
7	17	57%	Average
8	13	43%	Average
9	9	30%	Low
10	26	87%	Very high
11	24	80%	High
12	29	97%	Very High
13	16	53%	Average
14	25	83%	Very high
15	20	67%	High
16	24	80%	High
17	23	77%	High
18	23	77%	High
19	19	63%	High
20	12	40%	Low
21	26	87%	Very high
22	19	63%	High
23	25	83%	Very High
24	25	83%	Very High
25	23	77%	High
26	21	70%	High
27	18	60%	Average
28	18	60%	Average
29	19	63%	High
30	17	57%	Average
31	21	70%	High
32	18	60%	Average
33	20	67%	High
Total	641	2137	
Mean Score	19.42	64.75	High

Table 3 shows that it was possible to see that there was an improvement. According to the data, 6 out of 33 subjects, or 18%, Fourteen subjects of those polled, or 42 percent, received high marks. Pupils 2, 3, 11, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 22, 25, 26, 29, 31 and 33 received scores of 19, 23, 24, 20, 24, 23, 23, 19, 19, 23, 21, 19, 21 and 33.

It could be noted that pupils 5, 7, 8, 13, 27, 28, 30, and 32 received average scores. They had 17 points, 17 points, 13 points, 16 points, 18 points, 18 points, 17 points and, 18 points. As a result, 8 or 24% out of 33 subjects received average scores.

The data also revealed that five learners, or 15 percent, received low grades. They were learners 1, 4, 6, 9, and 20, and their scores were 11, 11, 10, 9, and 12. No learner received a meager post-test score, whereas seven learners received a meager pre-test score. The mean score increased by 7.78 points from 11.64 in the pre-test to 19.42 in the post-test.

The findings concluded that learners' knowledge increased after exposure to various learning materials. The teachers are encouraged to create contextualized learning materials to enhance the teaching and learning (Dewi and Primayana, 2019; Licorish, Owen, Daniel, and George, 2018).

received very high scores. Learners 10, 12, 14, 21, 23, and 24 received 26, 29, 25, 26, 25, and 25 compared to the pre-test, on which no one received a very high score.

Learning materials could help learners achieved tremendous success by assisting them in their learning process. This method facilitated learning by allowing the learner to explore the knowledge while also providing repetition. It played an integral part in enhancing educational achievement when correctly used (Almulla, 2020; Brewer and Movahedazarhouligh, 2018).

Actually, there was a solid positive meaningful connection between instructional resources and educational performance. In fact, the learners' performance was affected by the quality and quantity of teaching and learning materials. Therefore, poor performance could be attributed to inadequate teaching and learning materials and equipment (Ekperi, 2018; Issacar and Hesbon, 2021).

Table 4: Effectiveness of Contextualized Learning Materials among Grade 3 Learners

Variable	Df n-1	t-value		p-value	Description	Decision a = 0.05
		Computed	Tabular			
Pre-test Score versus Post-test Score	32	9.86	2.042	<u>0.0046</u>	significant	Reject H ₀

3.3 Effectiveness of Contextualized Learning Material in Teaching Mother Tongue 3

Table 4 displays the effectiveness of contextualized learning materials in teaching Mother Tongue 3. The data reveals that the computed t-value was 9.86 is greater than the tabular value of 2.045. This result indicates eliminating the null hypothesis in favor of the research hypothesis. This suggests that by employing contextualized learning materials, there was a substantial difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of grade 3 students in Mother Tongue. It implies that using contextualized learning materials in Mother Tongue was effective.

When a teacher applies new information, strategies, and skills to which students have gained new knowledge, learning occurs, improving academic performance and the ability to complete the given task independently. Contextualized learning materials can assist learners in understanding the concept and recognizing their ability to complete the assigned task (Brown and Palincsar, 2018; Chang, 2019; Häkkinen, Järvelä, Mäkitalo-Siegl, Ahonen, Näykki, and Valtonen, 2017).

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusions

Based on the data gathered, the following conclusions were established:

1. Prior to using contextualized learning material, most grade 3 learners had low achievement.
2. After the post-test activity, the subjects received high marks.
3. The Contextualized learning material effectively improved the performance in Mother Tongue.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings/conclusions of this study, it was recommended that:

1. Administrators may strengthen the full implementation of contextualized learning materials in the curriculum and use them across all learning areas to provide learners with meaningful learning experiences. Activities such as teacher training, seminars, and workshops, as well as forming partnerships with other agencies or offices to support this initiative, are suggested to do.
2. School heads may support teachers in this endeavor. It may include providing them with appropriate instructional resources, opportunities to engage in long-term professional learning experiences, and opportunities to collaborate on creating learning materials. It is recommended that materials be provided or procured to create learning materials.
3. The teachers may be encouraged to contextualize materials to enhance authentic, meaningful, and concrete learning by conducting and implementing the Learning Partnership Program (LPP), School Learning Action Cell (SLAC), and other related insets. As facilitators of learning, they are encouraged to develop, use, and adapt instructional and learning materials to improve students' academic performance.
4. The internal and external stakeholders may be encouraged to cooperate in all programs, projects, and activities, especially in supporting the teaching-learning process.
5. The learners may be encouraged to use these materials to reinforce learning.
6. The contextualized learning material is recommended for other grade levels. It may be suggested that the material be simplified, modified, and revised to meet the learners' learning needs.
7. Related research about contextualization of learning material and the implementation of Mother Tongue may highly be recommended.
8. The researcher may suggest contextualizing more materials in different learning areas. Further study about this topic may be conducted that will help improve the teaching-learning process. The researcher may also create new learning materials used during the pandemic and face-to-face contact.

REFERENCES

- [1] Agaton, C. B., & Cueto, L. J. (2021). Learning at home: Parents' lived experiences on distance learning during covid-19 pandemic in the Philippines. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(3), 901-911.
- [2] Agra, G., Formiga, N. S., Oliveira, P. S. D., Costa, M. M. L., Fernandes, M. D. G. M., & Nóbrega, M. M. L. D. (2019). Analysis of the concept of meaningful learning in light of the Ausubel's theory. *Revista brasileira de enfermagem*, 72, 248-255.
- [3] Ahmadi, D., & Reza, M. (2018). The use of technology in English language learning: A literature review. *International Journal of Research in English Education*, 3(2), 115-125.
- [4] Ajoke, A. R. (2017). The importance of instructional materials in teaching English as a second language. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 6(9), 36-44.
- [5] Alalwan, N., Cheng, L., Al-Samarraie, H., Yousef, R., Alzahrani, A. I., & Sarsam, S. M. (2020). Challenges and prospects of virtual reality and augmented reality utilization among primary school teachers: A developing country perspective. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 66, 100876.
- [6] Almulla, M. A. (2020). The effectiveness of the project-based learning (PBL) approach as a way to engage students in learning. *Sage Open*, 10(3), 2158244020938702.
- [7] Altemueller, L., & Lindquist, C. (2017). Flipped classroom instruction for inclusive learning. *British Journal of Special Education*, 44(3), 341-358.
- [8] Alieto, E. (2018). Language shift from English to Mother Tongue: Exploring language attitude and willingness to teach among pre-service teachers. *Online Submission*, 13(3), 134-146.

- [9] Amin, F. M., & Sundari, H. (2020). EFL students' preferences on digital platforms during emergency remote teaching: Video Conference, LMS, or Messenger Application?. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 7(2), 362-378.
- [10] Aminudin, A. (2018, September). Improving students' speaking skill through contextual teaching and learning (ctl) (A classroom action research of eighth grade students of smp negeri 2 angdana pandeglang in 2017/2018 academic year). In *proceeding AISELT (Annual International Seminar on English Language Teaching)* (Vol. 2, No. 2).
- [11] Anderson, R. C. (2018). Role of the reader's schema in comprehension, learning, and memory. In *Theoretical Models and Processes of Literacy* (pp. 136-145). Routledge.
- [12] Antonio, J. S. (2021). The learning delivery modalities in Catanduanes State University. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 2(11), 1061-1073.
- [13] Anwer, F. (2019). Activity-based teaching, student motivation and academic achievement. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 6(1), 154-170.
- [14] Anzaldo, G. D. (2021). Modular distance learning in the new normal education amidst Covid-19. *International Journal of Scientific Advances*, 2(3), 233-266.
- [15] Armstrong, P. (2016). Bloom's taxonomy. *Vanderbilt University Center for Teaching*.
- [16] Barkley, E. F., & Major, C. H. (2020). *Student engagement techniques: A handbook for college faculty*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [17] Barzilai, S., Zohar, A. R., & Mor-Hagani, S. (2018). Promoting integration of multiple texts: A review of instructional approaches and practices. *Educational psychology review*, 30(3), 973-999.
- [18] Berliner, D. C., & Rosenshine, B. (2017). *The acquisition of knowledge in the classroom* (pp. 375-396). Routledge.
- [19] Bishnoi, M. M. (2020). Flipped classroom and digitization: an inductive study on the learning framework for 21st century skill acquisition. *JETT*, 11(1), 30-45.
- [20] Boholano, H. (2017). Smart social networking: 21st century teaching and learning skills. *Research in Pedagogy*, 7(1), 21-29.
- [21] Brewer, R., & Movahedazarhouli, S. (2018). Successful stories and conflicts: A literature review on the effectiveness of flipped learning in higher education. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 34(4), 409-416.
- [22] Brown, A. L. (2017). Metacognitive development and reading. In *Theoretical issues in reading comprehension* (pp. 453-482). Routledge.
- [23] Brown, A. L., & Palincsar, A. S. (2018). *Guided, cooperative learning and individual knowledge acquisition* (pp. 393-451). Routledge.
- [24] Burden, P. R. (2020). *Classroom management: Creating a successful K-12 learning community*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [25] Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., ... & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive sampling: complex or simple? Research case examples. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 25(8), 652-661.
- [26] Cápuy, M. (2019). Enhancing the teaching of informatics through engaging experience. In *CSEU (1)* (pp. 453-460).
- [27] Çeliköz, N., Erişen, Y., & Şahin, M. (2019). Cognitive learning theories with emphasis on latent learning, gestalt and information processing theories. *Journal of Educational and Instructional Studies in the World*, 9(3).
- [28] Chalkiadaki, A. (2018). A systematic literature review of 21st century skills and competencies in primary education. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(3), 1-16.
- [29] Chang, B. (2019). Reflection in learning. *Online Learning*, 23(1), 95-110.
- [30] Chapelle, C. A., Kremmel, B., & Brindley, G. (2019). Assessment. In *An introduction to applied linguistics* (pp. 294-316). Routledge.

- [31] Chen, M. P., Wang, L. C., Zou, D., Lin, S. Y., Xie, H., & Tsai, C. C. (2020). Effects of captions and English proficiency on learning effectiveness, motivation and attitude in augmented-reality-enhanced theme-based contextualized EFL learning. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 1-31.
- [32] Clark, K. R. (2018). Learning theories: constructivism. *Radiologic Technology*, 90(2), 180-182.
- [33] Cooper, H., Lindsay, J. J., & Nye, B. (2000). Homework in the home: How student, family, and parenting-style differences relate to the homework process. *Contemporary educational psychology*, 25(4), 464-487.
- [34] Darling-Hammond, L., & Cook-Harvey, C. M. (2018). Educating the whole child: Improving school climate to support student success. *Learning Policy Institute*.
- [35] Dastpak, M., Behjat, F., & Taghinezhad, A. (2017). A comparative study of Vygotsky's perspectives on child language development with nativism and behaviorism. *Online Submission*, 5(2), 230-238.
- [36] Dekker, D. E. (2017). *Finally shedding the past: Filipino teachers negotiate their identities within a new mother-tongue-based multilingual education policy landscape* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Toronto (Canada)).
- [37] De Los Reyes, R. A. (2019). Translanguaging in multilingual third grade ESL classrooms in Mindanao, Philippines. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 16(3), 302-316.
- [38] Deslauriers, L., McCarty, L. S., Miller, K., Callaghan, K., & Kestin, G. (2019). Measuring actual learning versus feeling of learning in response to being actively engaged in the classroom. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(39), 19251-19257.
- [39] Dewi, P. Y. A., & Primayana, K. H. (2019). Effect of learning module with setting contextual teaching and learning to increase the understanding of concepts. *International Journal of Education and Learning*, 1(1), 19-26.
- [40] Duran, D. (2017). Learning-by-teaching. Evidence and implications as a pedagogical mechanism. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 54(5), 476-484.
- [41] Đurišić, M., & Bunijevac, M. (2017). Parental involvement as an important factor for successful education. *Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal*, 7(3), 137-153.
- [42] Ekperi, P. M. (2018). Impact of teacher characteristics on students' academic performance in public secondary schools. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 2(12), 514-519.
- [43] Elfrink, T. R., Goldberg, J. M., Schreurs, K. M., Bohlmeijer, E. T., & Clarke, A. M. (2017). Positive educative programme: A whole school approach to supporting children's well-being and creating a positive school climate: a pilot study. *Health Education*.
- [44] Emaliana, I. (2017). Teacher-centered or student-centered learning approach to promote learning?. *Jurnal Sosial Humaniora (JSH)*, 10(2), 59-70.
- [45] Erdoğan, V. (2019). Integrating 4C skills of 21st century into 4 language skills in EFL classes. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 7(11), 113-124.
- [46] Eslit, E. R. (2017). Binisaya instruction: Facing the MTB-MLE challenges head-on. *Research Gate*.
- [47] Ferreira, M., Martinsone, B., & Talić, S. (2020). Promoting sustainable social emotional learning at school through relationship-centered learning environment, teaching methods and formative assessment. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 22(1), 21-36.
- [48] Fisher, D., Frey, N., & Hattie, J. (2020). *The distance learning playbook, grades K-12: Teaching for engagement and impact in any setting*. Corwin Press.
- [49] Frey, N., Fisher, D., & Smith, D. (2019). *All learning is social and emotional: Helping students develop essential skills for the classroom and beyond*. ASCD.
- [50] Gay, G. (2018). *Culturally responsive teaching: Theory, research, and practice*. Teachers college press.
- [51] Gehlbach, H., & Artino, A. R. (2018). The survey checklist (manifesto). *Academic Medicine*, 93(3), 360-366.

- [52] Gess-Newsome, J., Taylor, J. A., Carlson, J., Gardner, A. L., Wilson, C. D., & Stuhlsatz, M. A. (2019). Teacher pedagogical content knowledge, practice, and student achievement. *International Journal of Science Education*, 41(7), 944-963.
- [53] Ghaith, G. M. (2018). Teacher perceptions of the challenges of implementing concrete and conceptual cooperative learning. *Issues in Educational Research*, 28(2), 385-404.
- [54] Gómez-Pablos, V. B., del Pozo, M. M., & Muñoz-Repiso, A. G. V. (2017). Project-based learning (PBL) through the incorporation of digital technologies: An evaluation based on the experience of serving teachers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 68, 501-512.
- [55] Goss, P., & Sonnemann, J. (2017). *Engaging students: Creating classrooms that improve learning*. Grattan Institute.
- [56] Häkkinen, P., Järvelä, S., Mäkitalo-Siegl, K., Ahonen, A., Näykki, P., & Valtonen, T. (2017). Preparing teacher-students for twenty-first-century learning practices (PREP 21): a framework for enhancing collaborative problem-solving and strategic learning skills. *Teachers and Teaching*, 23(1), 25-41.
- [57] Henriksen, D., Richardson, C., & Mehta, R. (2017). Design thinking: A creative approach to educational problems of practice. *Thinking skills and Creativity*, 26, 140-153.
- [58] Hoidn, S., & Reusser, K. (2020). Foundations of student-centered learning and teaching. In *The Routledge International Handbook of Student-Centered Learning and Teaching in Higher Education* (pp. 17-46). Routledge.
- [59] Huijgen, T., van de Grift, W., van Boxtel, C., & Holthuis, P. (2018). Promoting historical contextualization: The development and testing of a pedagogy. *Journal of curriculum studies*, 50(3), 410-434.
- [60] Husnora, M. (2021). Bloom's taxonomy and its role in academic writing and reading skills training at English classes. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(3), 746-750.
- [61] Iballa, S., & Dela Cruz, A. E. (2019). Assessment on the cultural competencies of Araling Panlipunan teachers in public secondary schools of Baras district division of Rizal. Available at SSRN 3687890.
- [62] Islam, S., Baharun, H., Muali, C., Ghufron, M. I., el Iq Bali, M., Wijaya, M., & Marzuki, I. (2018, November). To boost students' motivation and achievement through blended learning. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1114, No. 1, p. 012046). IOP Publishing.
- [63] Issacar, N., & Hesbon, A. O. (2021). Instructional learning materials' use and students academic outcomes in private secondary schools in Rwanda: A Case Study of Nyarugenge District. *Journal of Education*, 4(7), 76-93.
- [64] Jaca, C. A. L., & Lopez-Baroman, J. L. (2021). Challenges and extent of readiness among teachers in the implementation of the Kindergarten curriculum in select public elementary schools in the Philippines. *International Journal of Elementary Education*, 10(4), 134.
- [65] Jan, H. (2017). Teacher of 21st century: Characteristics and development. *Research on Humanities and Social sciences*, 7(9), 50-54.
- [66] Jimenez, E. C. (2020). Motivating factors of teachers in developing supplementary learning materials (SLMs). *Online Submission*, 8(5), 108-113.
- [67] Johnson, D., Johnson R. & Smith K. (2018). Active learning: Co-operation in the college classroom. *Edina, MB: Interaction Book Co.*
- [68] Kaymakamoglu, S. E. (2018). Teachers' beliefs, perceived practice and actual classroom practice in relation to traditional (teacher-centered) and constructivist (learner-centered) teaching (note 1). *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(1), 29-37.
- [69] Kimberlin, C. L., & Winterstein, A. G. (2008). Validity and reliability of measurement instruments used in research. *American journal of health-system pharmacy*, 65(23), 2276-2284.
- [70] Kintsch, W. (2018). Revisiting the construction—integration model of text comprehension and its implications for instruction. In *theoretical models and processes of literacy* (pp. 178-203). Routledge.

- [71] Kintu, M. J., Zhu, C., & Kagambe, E. (2017). Blended learning effectiveness: the relationship between student characteristics, design features and outcomes. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 14(1), 1-20.
- [72] Kirkpatrick, A. (2017). Language education policy among the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). *European Journal of Language Policy*, 9(1), 7-25.
- [73] Klar, S., & Leeper, T. J. (2019). Identities and intersectionality: a case for Purposive sampling in Survey-Experimental research. *Experimental methods in survey research: Techniques that combine random sampling with random assignment*, 419-433.
- [74] Koh, A. W. L., Lee, S. C., & Lim, S. W. H. (2018). The learning benefits of teaching: A retrieval practice hypothesis. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 32(3), 401-410.
- [75] Kuzminov, Y., Sorokin, P., & Froumin, I. (2019). Generic and specific skills as components of human capital: New challenges for education theory and practice. *ФОРСАЙТ*, 13 (2 (eng)).
- [76] Lang-ay, P. L. D., & Sannadan, J. G. M. (2021). Mother tongue based language education in Philippines and Cambodia: A Comparative Study.
- [77] Lara, L., & Saracostti, M. (2019). Effect of parental involvement on children's academic achievement in Chile. *Frontiers in psychology*, 1464.
- [78] Lau, E. Y. H., & Lee, K. (2021). Parents' views on young children's distance learning and screen time during COVID-19 class suspension in Hong Kong. *Early Education and Development*, 32(6), 863-880.
- [79] Lee, E., & Hannafin, M. J. (2016). A design framework for enhancing engagement in student-centered learning: Own it, learn it, and share it. *Educational technology research and development*, 64(4), 707-734.
- [80] Lee, H. Y., Hamid, M. O., & Hardy, I. (2021). Language and education policies in Southeast Asia: reorienting towards multilingualism-as-resource. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 1-19.
- [81] Lee, W. O., & Tan, J. P. L. (2018). The new roles for twenty-first-century teachers: Facilitator, knowledge broker, and pedagogical weaver. In *The teacher's role in the changing globalizing world* (pp. 11-31). Brill.
- [82] Leighton, L. J., & Crompton, H. (2017). Augmented reality in K-12 education. In *Mobile technologies and augmented reality in open education* (pp. 281-290). IGI Global.
- [83] Lerch, J. C., & Buckner, E. (2018). From education for peace to education in conflict: Changes in UNESCO discourse, 1945–2015. *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 16(1), 27-48.
- [84] Licorish, S. A., Owen, H. E., Daniel, B., & George, J. L. (2018). Students' perception of Kahoot!'s influence on teaching and learning. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 13(1), 1-23.
- [85] Little, C. (2017). Designing and implementing concept-based curriculum. In *Curriculum for high ability learners* (pp. 43-59). Springer, Singapore.
- [86] Lorbis, J. C. C. (2019). Utilization of contextualized teaching and learning (CTL) approach in grade two Araling Panlipunan. *Online Submission*.
- [87] Lotulung, C. F., Ibrahim, N., & Tumurang, H. (2018). Effectiveness of learning method contextual teaching learning (ctl) for increasing learning outcomes of entrepreneurship education. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology-TOJET*, 17(3), 37-46.
- [88] Luk, J. C., & Lin, A. M. (2017). *Classroom interactions as cross-cultural encounters: Native speakers in EFL lessons*. Routledge.
- [89] Malik, R. S. (2018). Educational challenges in 21st century and sustainable development. *Journal of Sustainable Development Education and Research*, 2(1), 9-20.
- [90] Mangila, B. B. (2019). Institutionalizing a mother tongue-based approach in teaching multicultural classrooms: A closer look at elementary teachers' experiences. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 6(2), 34-39.

- [91] Manning, M. L., Baruth, L. G., & Lee, G. L. (2017). *Multicultural education of children and adolescents*. Routledge.
- [92] Mezirow, J. (2018). Transformative learning theory. In *Contemporary theories of learning* (pp. 114-128). Routledge.
- [93] Mhlongo, S. R. B. (2019). *Exploring Grade 10 teachers' experiences of mother tongue reading habits: case studies of two selected high schools in KwaZulu-Natal* (Doctoral dissertation).
- [94] Mickan, P., & Wallace, I. (Eds.). (2019). *The Routledge handbook of language education curriculum design*. Routledge.
- [95] Monje, J. D., Orbeta, A. C., Francisco-Abrigo, K. A., & Capones, E. M. (2019). "Starting where the children are": A process evaluation of the mother tongue-based multilingual education implementation (No. 2019-06). PIDS Discussion Paper Series.
- [96] Moradi, H. (2018). Self-directed learning in language teaching-learning processes. *Modern Journal of Language Teaching Methods (MJLTM)*, 8(6), 59-64.
- [97] Moust, J., Bouhuijs, P., & Schmidt, H. (2021). *Introduction to problem-based learning: A guide for students*. Routledge.
- [98] Muijs, D., & Reynolds, D. (2017). *Effective teaching: Evidence and practice*. Sage.
- [99] Mupa, P., & Isaac Chinooneka, T. (2019). Factors contributing to ineffective teaching and learning in primary schools: Why are schools in decadence.
- [100] Namanya, S. J. C. (2017, December). The effects of mother tongue-based multilingual education on the English literacy of children in Silang, Philippines. In *International Forum Journal* (Vol. 20, No. 2, pp. 160-177).
- [101] Natividad, E. (2021). Perceived effectiveness of self learning modules in the implementation of modular distance learning in the elementary level. Available at SSRN 3889429.
- [102] Newman, K., Gentile, E., & Cruz, D. A. N. (2020). Education for innovation: Sorting fact from fiction.
- [103] Ocampo, D. J., Rufino, R., & Gonzales, J. F. (2021). Participatory policy formulation on indigenous peoples' education in the K to 12 basic education program in the Philippines. In *Minding the Marginalized Students Through Inclusion, Justice, and Hope*. Emerald Publishing Limited.
- [104] Olson, D. R. (2017). The languages of instruction: The literate bias of schooling. In *Schooling and the acquisition of knowledge* (pp. 65-89). Routledge.
- [105] Pandey, P., & Pandey, M. M. (2021). *Research methodology tools and techniques*. Bridge Center.
- [106] Panganiban, G. L., & Madrigal, D. V. (2021). Grappling with the learning modules: Experience of public elementary pupils attending English written modular classes. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 20, 263.
- [107] Papanastasiou, G., Drigas, A., Skianis, C., Lytras, M., & Papanastasiou, E. (2019). Virtual and augmented reality effects on K-12, higher and tertiary education students' twenty-first century skills. *Virtual Reality*, 23(4), 425-436.
- [108] Parba, J. (2018). Teachers' shifting language ideologies and teaching practices in Philippine mother tongue classrooms. *Linguistics and Education*, 47, 27-35.
- [109] Perez, N. B. (2019). A comparative study of the mtb-mle programs in Southeast Asian countries. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 3(6), 47-55.
- [110] Philippines Department of Education Order No. 012, s. 2020. Adoption of the basic education learning continuity plan for school year 2020 – 2021 in light of the covid-19 public health emergency. June 19, 2020
- [111] Philippines Department of Education Order No. 16, s. 2012. Guidelines on the implementation of the mother tongue-based multi-lingual education. February 17, 2012
- [112] Pinter, A. (2017). *Teaching young language learners*. Oxford University Press.

- [113] Pitzer, J., & Skinner, E. (2017). Predictors of changes in students' motivational resilience over the school year: The roles of teacher support, self-appraisals, and emotional reactivity. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 41(1), 15-29.
- [114] Rao, P. S. (2019). The effective use of authentic materials in the English language classrooms. *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, 7(1), 1-8.
- [115] Reimers, F., Schleicher, A., Saavedra, J., & Tuominen, S. (2020). Supporting the continuation of teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Oecd*, 1(1), 1-38.
- [116] Renkl, A., & Scheiter, K. (2017). Studying visual displays: How to instructionally support learning. *Educational Psychology Review*, 29(3), 599-621.
- [117] Republic Act No. 10533. (2013). Implementing rules and regulations of the enhanced basic education act of 2013.
- [118] Rivera, J. G. (2017). Articulating the foundations of Philippine K to 12 curriculum: learner-centeredness. *AsTEN Journal of Teacher Education*, 2(1).
- [119] Roser, M., & Ortiz-Ospina, E. (2017). Global rise of education. *Our World in Data*.
- [120] Roumell, E. A. (2019). Priming adult learners for learning transfer: Beyond content and delivery. *Adult Learning*, 30(1), 15-22.
- [121] Sah, P. K. (2022). English medium instruction in South Asia's multilingual schools: unpacking the dynamics of ideological orientations, policy/practices, and democratic questions. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 25(2), 742-755.
- [122] Saville-Troike, M., & Barto, K. (2017). *Introducing second language acquisition*. Cambridge University Press.
- [123] Schonert-Reichl, K. A. (2017). Social and emotional learning and teachers. *The future of children*, 137-155.
- [124] Serin, H. (2018). A comparison of teacher-centered and student-centered approaches in educational settings. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 5(1), 164-167.
- [125] Shawky, D., & Badawi, A. (2018, February). A reinforcement learning-based adaptive learning system. In *International Conference on Advanced Machine Learning Technologies and Applications* (pp. 221-231). Springer, Cham.
- [126] Slavin, R. E. (2019). *Educational psychology: Theory and practice*.
- [127] Smallhorn, M. (2017). The flipped classroom: A learning model to increase student engagement not academic achievement. *Student Success*, 8(2), 43-53.
- [128] Sporns, O., & Betzel, R. F. (2016). Modular brain networks. *Annual review of psychology*, 67, 613-640.
- [129] Sprenger, M. (2018). *How to teach so students remember*. ASCD.
- [130] Stern, J., Ferraro, K., & Mohnkern, J. (2017). *Tools for teaching conceptual understanding, secondary: Designing lessons and assessments for deep learning*. Corwin Press.
- [131] Stoop, C. (2017). Children's rights to mother-tongue education in a multilingual world: a comparative analysis between South Africa and Germany. *Potchefstroom Electronic Law Journal/Potchefstroomse Elektroniese Regsblad*, 20(1).
- [132] Strickland-Davis, S., Kosloski, M., & Reed, P. A. (2020). The impact of professional development grounded in social learning on community college faculty efficacy. *Community College Journal of Research and Practice*, 44(7), 492-507.
- [133] Stronge, J. H. (2018). *Qualities of effective teachers*. Ascd.
- [134] Suryawati, E., & Osman, K. (2017). Contextual learning: Innovative approach towards the development of students' scientific attitude and natural science performance. *Eurasia Journal of mathematics, science and technology education*, 14(1), 61-76.

- [135] Taber, K. S. (2020). Mediated learning leading development—the social development theory of Lev Vygotsky. In *Science education in theory and practice* (pp. 277-291). Springer, Cham.
- [136] Tadeo, G. P., & Queroda, P. G. (2020). Relationship of the use of mother tongue-based multilingual education to the English learning competencies of pupils. *ASEAN Journal of Basic and Higher Education*, 1.
- [137] Tomlinson, B., & Masuhara, H. (2017). *The complete guide to the theory and practice of materials development for language learning*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [138] Tomlinson, C. A. (2017). *How to differentiate instruction in academically diverse classrooms*. ASCD.
- [139] Tsortanidou, X., Daradoumis, T., & Barberá, E. (2020). Developing social-emotional skills through imaginative teaching methods in elementary education. *Early Child Development and Care*, 1-16.
- [140] Tsui, A. B., & Tollefson, J. W. (2017). 1 language policy and the construction of national cultural identity. In *Language policy, culture, and identity in Asian contexts* (pp. 1-22). Routledge.
- [141] Tupas, R., & Martin, I. P. (2017). Bilingual and mother tongue-based multilingual education in the Philippines. *Bilingual and multilingual education*, 10, 247-258.
- [142] Us Saqlain, N., Shafqat, A., & Hassan, A. (2020). Perception analysis of English language teachers about use of contextualized text for teaching ESP. *The Asian ESP Journal*, 16(5.1), 275-299.
- [143] Van Teijlingen, E. R., & Hundley, V. (2001). The importance of pilot studies.
- [144] Vercellotti, M. L. (2018). Do interactive learning spaces increase student achievement? A comparison of classroom context. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 19(3), 197-210.
- [145] Voskoglou, M. G. (2019). A Markov chain application on the levels of the Bloom's taxonomy of learning objectives. *Am J Educ Res*, 7(3), 294-8.
- [146] Yan, Z. (2020). Self-assessment in the process of self-regulated learning and its relationship with academic achievement. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 45(2), 224-238.